

Acute Small Bowel Obstruction

Cesár Alberto Ortíz Orozco¹, Jimena Alvarez del Castillo Gonzalez², Félix Osuna Gutiérrez³, José María Zepeda Torres⁴

¹Dr Juan I Menchaca Public Hospital of Guadalajara, General Surgery Department

^{2,3,4}Institution: Autonomous University of Guadalajara, Guadalajara, Jalisco, Mexico

ABSTRACT

An intestinal obstruction can be divided into mechanical or functional of the small intestine or the large intestine. This can happen if the lumen of the intestine is partially or completely blocked. Within the common clinical picture you can find abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, constipation to constipation and abdominal distension. Small bowel obstructions occur more frequently than large bowel obstructions. One of the classifications to be able to divide them is in complete, closed handle or partial. The prompt identification of this pathology as well as indicating an opportune treatment is key for the survival of the patients.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
23 July 2022

Available on:
<https://ijmscr.org/>

INTRODUCTION

Post surgical adhesions are the main cause of small bowel obstruction (60%), resulting in 8 days of hospitalization, with a mortality of 3%. Some 20 to 30% require surgical treatment, with a hospital stay of about 10 days. Definition "Peritoneal adhesion" or simply "adhesion". Fibrous tissue that connects surfaces or organs to the peritoneal cavity.^{1,2}

Adhesions are the main cause of a surgical emergency, characterized by abdominal pain, vomiting, bloating and constipation.^{3,4}

The mechanical etiologies of intestinal obstruction can be classified as follows:

	Extrinsic bowel obstruction	Intrinsic bowel obstruction	
		Intramural bowel obstruction	Intraluminal bowel obstruction
Etiology	<ul style="list-style-type: none">External compression of the bowel <ul style="list-style-type: none">Bowel adhesionsVolvulusIncarcerated hernia (e.g., inguinal hernia, umbilical hernia, femoral hernia)Intraabdominal mass (e.g., metastatic lymphadenopathy, large intraabdominal abscess or cyst)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">The underlying etiology arises from the intestinal wall.<ul style="list-style-type: none">Strictures (e.g., IBD, tuberculosis)Intestinal tumors (e.g., colorectal carcinoma, lymphoma)DiverticulitisIntussusception	<ul style="list-style-type: none">The obstructing agent lies within the gastrointestinal lumen.<ul style="list-style-type: none">Gallstone ileusForeign body ingestionBezoars (e.g., phytobezoars)Fecal impactionHelminthic infection

The causes of obstruction of non-adherent etiology are: incarcerated hernias, obstructive lesions both malignant and benign, as well as other infrequent causes such as bezoars, inflammatory bowel disease and volvulus.^{5,6}

The confirmatory diagnosis of suspected adhesive etiology is during surgical treatment; non-invasive diagnostic methods are performed with a good anamnesis and clinical history (previous episodes) or exclusion of other causes by computed tomography.^{6,7}

Adhesiolysis: Release adhesions by sharp or blunt dissection during surgery.⁷

Adhesiolysis complicated: Inadvertent damage when performing adhesiolysis, regularly to the intestine.⁷

Bowel injury classification

- Seromuscular injury: Damage to the visceral peritoneum (serosa) and smooth muscle layer of the intestine. The

Acute Small Bowel Obstruction

wilbeest of the intestine or leakage of its contents is not visible.⁸

- Enterotomy: Full-thickness injury to the bowel; the mucosal lining or lumen of the bowel is visible or there may be leakage of bowel contents.⁹
- Delayed diagnostic perforation: Injuries during surgery that are not initially recognized. Typically the abdomen is closed at the end of surgery with bowel injury still in place, deteriorating the patient post-surgery.⁹

EPIDEMIOLOGY

Risk of small bowel obstruction from surgery:

1. Colorectal surgery.
2. Oncogynecologic surgery.
3. Pediatric surgery.

1 in 10 patients will develop at least one patient with small bowel obstruction three years after colectomy. 12% of patients managed with non-surgical treatment are readmitted to hospital for bowel obstruction after one year and 20% after five years; after surgical treatment, the percentage is 8% and 16% respectively.^{10,11,12,13}

PREVENTION

There is evidence that the incidence is lower after laparoscopy. Peritoneal damage is less with bipolar electrocautery and ultrasonic devices compared to monopolar electrocautery.¹⁴

ADHESION BARRIERS

Adjuvants for peritoneal administration that can effectively reduce the formation of adhesions. They exist as solid membranes, gels and liquids. They act by separating the damaged surfaces of the peritoneum, allowing them to heal without creating fibrous tissue that leads to adhesions.¹⁵

- Hyaluronate carboxymethylcellulose.
- Regenerated oxidized cellulose.
- Icodextrin.
- Polyethylene glycol.

MEDICAL HISTORY AND PHYSICAL EXAMINATION

It is important to investigate potential causes of small bowel obstruction due to adhesions, nutritional status and signs of dehydration. They traditionally present with colicky abdominal pain, bloating, nausea with or without vomiting, and may or may not defecate. Patients with incomplete obstruction may present with watery diarrhea. During the examination we must look for signs of peritonitis that could reveal strangulation or ischemia.^{16, 17,18}

LABORATORY: It is indicated to request a blood biometry, lactate, serum electrolytes, reactive protein C and BUN / Creatinine ratio. The values that may indicate peritonitis are CRP >75 and leukocytosis >100,000/mm³.^{19,20}

X-RAYS: In case of suspicion of high obstruction we must look for the tria 1) Hydro-aerial levels, 2) Distension, 3) Absence of gas in the colon.^{21,22}

CONTRASTED STUDIES: The absence of contrast 24 hours after administration is highly indicative of failure of conservative treatment. Some authors point out that it can serve as therapeutic management.^{23,24}

COMPUTERIZED TOMOGRAPHY: It is capable of detecting strangulation and the need for surgery with 90% effectiveness. Signs of closed loop, ischemia and leaking fluid are suggestive of the need for surgery.^{25,26}

Fig.1 Significant dilatation of the mid and distal small bowel loops can be seen.

Acute Small Bowel Obstruction

MANAGEMENT/TREATMENT

Initial Handling

Conservative management should be considered in the first instance in patients with small bowel obstruction due to adhesions unless there is evidence of peritonitis, strangulation, or ischemia. The cornerstone of conservative management is the nasogastric tube or gastrointestinal tube, which is effective in 70 to 90% of cases.²⁷

Conservative management should include fluid resuscitation, electrolyte correction, nutritional support and prevention of aspiration. Management for at least 72 hours is considered appropriate and safe.²⁸

Surgical treatment

Historically, exploratory laparotomy is the standard treatment, but laparoscopy has been included with benefits such as a lower incidence of adhesions, early return of bowel movements and less postoperative pain and hospitalization time; however, laparoscopy in an overly distended bowel may increase the risk of complications such as enterotomy or late diagnostic perforations.^{29,30,31}

CONCLUSION

Intestinal obstruction is a highly frequent surgical emergency of high clinical importance. The constant increase in abdominal and pelvic surgeries has caused the number of adhesions, as well as intestinal obstructions to increase.

The variants that exist such as the etiology, the site of obstruction, the viability of the intestine as well as the delay in diagnosis are key to survival.

REFERENCES

- I. Griffiths S, Glancy DG. Intestinal obstruction. *Surgery* ; 35(3): p.3. doi: 10.1016/j.mpsur.2016.12.005.
- II. Diamond M, Lee J, LeBedis CA. Small Bowel Obstruction and Ischemia. *Radiol Clin North Am* .2019; 57(4): p.689-703. doi: 10.1016/j.rcl.2019.02.002.
- III. Jackson P, Vigiola Cruz M. Intestinal Obstruction: Evaluation and Management. *Am Fam Physician* .2018; 98(6): p.362-367. pmid: 30215917. pmid: 30215917
- IV. Jaffe T, Thompson WM. Large-Bowel Obstruction in the Adult: Classic Radiographic and CT Findings, Etiology, and Mimics. *Radiology* .2015; 275(3): p.651-663. doi: 10.1148/radiol.2015140916.
- V. Rami Reddy SR, Cappell MS. A Systematic Review of the Clinical Presentation, Diagnosis, and Treatment of Small Bowel Obstruction. *Curr Gastroenterol Rep* .2017; 19(6): p.28. doi: 10.1007/s11894-017-0566-9.
- VI. Hayden GE, Sprouse KL. Bowel Obstruction and Hernia. *Emerg Med Clin North Am* .2011; 29(2): p.319-345. doi: 10.1016/j.emc.2011.01.004.
- VII. Katz SD, Baker EM, et al.. American College of Radiology ACR Appropriateness Criteria® Suspected Small-Bowel Obstruction. <https://acsearch.acr.org/docs/69476/Narrative/>. Updated: December 31, 2012
- VIII. Pisano M, Zorcolo L, Merli C, et al. 2017 WSES guidelines on colon and rectal cancer emergencies: obstruction and perforation. *World Journal of Emergency Surgery* .2018; 13(1): p.36. doi: 10.1186/s13017-018-0192-3.
- IX. Maung AA, Johnson DC, Piper GL, et al. Evaluation and management of small-bowel obstruction. *Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery* .2012; 73(5): p.S362-S369. doi: 10.1097/ta.0b013e31827019de.
- X. Long B, Robertson J, Koyfman A. Emergency Medicine Evaluation and Management of Small Bowel Obstruction: Evidence-Based Recommendations. *J Emerg Med* .2019; 56(2): p.166-176. doi: 10.1016/j.jemermed.2018.10.024.
- XI. Macaluso C, McNamara. Evaluation and management of acute abdominal pain in the emergency department. *International Journal of General Medicine* .2012; p.789. doi: 10.2147/ijgm.s25936.
- XII. Bower KL, Lollar DI, Williams SL, Adkins FC, Luyimbazi DT, Bower CE. Small Bowel Obstruction. *Surg Clin North Am* .2018; 98(5): p.945-971. doi: 10.1016/j.suc.2018.05.007.
- XIII. Ten Broek RPG, Krielen P, Di Saverio S, et al. Bologna guidelines for diagnosis and management of adhesive small bowel obstruction (ASBO): 2017 update of the evidence-based guidelines from the world society of emergency surgery ASBO working group. *World Journal of Emergency Surgery* .2018; 13(1): p.24. doi: 10.1186/s13017-018-0185-2.
- XIV. Chang KJ, Marin D, Kim DH, et al. ACR Appropriateness Criteria® Suspected Small-Bowel Obstruction. *J Am Coll Radiol* .2020; 17(5): p.S305-S314. doi: 10.1016/j.jacr.2020.01.025.
- XV. Mian M, Swamy N, Angtuaco T. Imaging in Acute Intestinal Obstruction. *Contemporary Diagnostic Radiology* .2019; 42(24): p.1-7. doi: 10.1097/01.cdr.0000612380.42855.c0.
- XVI. Chuong AM, Corno L et al. Assessment of Bowel Wall Enhancement for the Diagnosis of Intestinal Ischemia in Patients with Small Bowel Obstruction: Value of Adding Unenhanced CT to Contrast-enhanced CT.... *Radiology* .2016; 280(1): p.98-107. doi: 10.1148/radiol.2016151029.
- XVII. Li Z, Zhang L, Liu X, Yuan F, Song B. Diagnostic utility of CT for small bowel obstruction: systematic review and meta-analysis.... *PLoS ONE* .2019; 14(12): p.e0226740. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0226740.

Acute Small Bowel Obstruction

- XVIII. Cartwright SL, Knudson MP. Diagnostic Imaging of Acute Abdominal Pain in Adults. *American Academy of Family Physicians* .2015; 91(7): p.452-9. pmid: 25884745. pmid: 25884745.
- XIX. Pourmand A, Dimbil U, Drake A, Shokoohi H. The Accuracy of Point-of-Care Ultrasound in Detecting Small Bowel Obstruction in Emergency Department. *Emergency Medicine International* .2018; 2018: p.1-5. doi: 10.1155/2018/3684081.
- XX. Taylor MR, Lalani N. Adult Small Bowel Obstruction. *Academic Emergency Medicine* .2013; 20(6): p.527-544. doi: 10.1111/acem.12150.].
- XXI. Guttman J, Stone MB, Kimberly HH, Rempell JS. Point-of-care ultrasonography for the diagnosis of small bowel obstruction in the emergency department. *CJEM* .2015; 17(2): p.206-209. doi: 10.2310/8000.2014.141382.
- XXII. Jang TB, Schindler D, Kaji AH. Bedside ultrasonography for the detection of small bowel obstruction in the emergency department. *Emerg Med J* .2010; 28(8): p.676-678. doi: 10.1136/emj.2010.095729
- XXIII. Abu-Zidan F, Hefny A, Corr P. The role of ultrasound in the management of intestinal obstruction. *J Emerg Trauma Shock* .2012; 5(1): p.84. doi: 10.4103/0974-2700.93109.
- XXIV. Alzaraa A, Krzysztof K, Uwechue R, Tee M, Selvasekar C. Apple-core lesion of the colon: a case report. *Cases J* .2009; 2(1): p.7275. doi: 10.4076/1757-1626-2-7275
- XXV. Landercasper J, Cogbill TH, Merry WH, et al. Long-term Outcome After Hospitalization for Small-Bowel Obstruction. *Arch Surg* .1993; 128(7): p.765-771. doi: 10.1001/archsurg.1993.01420190059008.
- XXVI. Batke, Cappell. Adynamic Ileus and Acute Colonic Pseudo-Obstruction. *The Medical Clinics of North America* .; 92: p.649-670. doi: 10.1016/j.mcna.2008.01.002
- XXVII. Nobie BA, Talavera F. Small-Bowel Obstruction. In: Dronen SC *Small-Bowel Obstruction*. New York, NY: WebMD. <http://emedicine.medscape.com/article/774140-overview>.
- XXVIII. Di Saverio S, Coccolini F, Galati M, et al. Bologna guidelines for diagnosis and management of adhesive small bowel obstruction (ASBO): 2013 update of the evidence-based guidelines from the world society of emergency surgery ASBO working group. *World Journal of Emergency Surgery* .2013; 8(1): p.42. doi: 10.1186/1749-7922-8-42.
- XXIX. Keenan JE, Turley RS, McCoy CC, Migaly J, Shapiro ML, Scarborough JE. Trials of nonoperative management exceeding 3 days are associated with increased morbidity in patients undergoing surgery for uncomplicated adhesive small bowel obstruction. *The journal of trauma and acute care surgery* .2014; 76(6): p.1367-72. doi: 10.1097/TA.0000000000000246.
- XXX. Harrison ME, Anderson MA, Appalaneni V, et al. The role of endoscopy in the management of patients with known and suspected colonic obstruction and pseudo-obstruction. *Gastrointest Endosc* .2010; 71(4): p.669-679. doi: 10.1016/j.gie.2009.11.027.
- XXXI. Sugawa C. Endoscopic management of foreign bodies in the upper gastrointestinal tract: A review. *World Journal of Gastrointestinal Endoscopy* .2014; 6(10): p.475. doi: 10.4253/wjge.v6.i10.475.